

Teachers' Workload and Job Satisfaction of Newly Hired Teachers in Congressional District IV, Batangas Province

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Abstract

The study aimed to examine how various duties and responsibilities relate to educators' job satisfaction. Specifically, it focused on the workload and job satisfaction of newly hired teachers (0-3 years in service) in CD IV, Batangas Province. Descriptive-correlational research was utilized with researcher-made questionnaires to assess the degree of job satisfaction, the extent of workload manifestation, and the challenges encountered by teachers. By gaining a understanding of these experiences, the education system can be better equipped to provide appropriate support and foster an environment where educators are able to thrive both professionally and personally.

The sample of 219 teachers from 503 study population was obtained through Raosoft sample size calculator, Statistical tools used were frequency, weighted mean, ranking, and Pearson's r correlation coefficient.

Findings reveal that newly hired teachers are highly satisfied with their teaching-related workload, teaching load, and the extra-curricular and non-teaching duties. Furthermore, newly hired teachers' extent of manifestation of workload difficulty in terms of teaching retention, motivation and engagement, and in professional commitment are highly manifested.

In conclusion, there is a significant relationship between teaching-related work and extra curricular and non teaching duties to the extent of manifestation of workload difficulty in terms of teacher retention. Meaning, balance and demands of instructional responsibilities directly affect teachers' willingness and ability to remain in the profession. When teaching loads and other tasks are manageable, teachers experience less difficulty, leading to higher satisfaction and stronger retention. Nevertheless, engaging activities for teachers have been proposed to enhance teachers' job satisfaction.

Keywords: *Teachers' Workload, Job Satisfaction, Newly Hired Teachers; teaching load, teaching-related workload*

Introduction

Teaching is one of the most respected professions in the world. It is the process of facilitating learning that involves sharing knowledge, developing skills, and shaping the character of learners. It requires a deep understanding of content and learners' needs. It is a dynamic profession that calls for patience, empathy, and continuous learning. In the Philippines, Filipinos consider teaching a noble and essential profession. Here, teachers play a central role in the nation's development by shaping the minds and values of future generations. However, the growing number of responsibilities placed upon teachers has raised concerns about their overall well-being and job satisfaction.

As a newly hired public school teacher, the researcher has personally experienced the demands of the profession. Aside from preparing daily lessons and attending to students' academic needs, the researcher also found herself involved in various tasks, report submissions, documentation requirements, school programs, and participation in training and meetings. The researcher is aware that the duties mentioned earlier are all part of teachers' role but through day-to-day experiences and casual conversations with fellow new teachers, the researcher noticed that teachers have common sentiments, and those pertain to heavy workloads.

Thus, the study aims to know how various duties and responsibilities affect educators' motivation and well-being. The researcher hopes that the findings of this study, no matter how modest, may offer insights for school administrators, policy makers, and education stakeholders.

This study aimed to determine the teacher's workload and job satisfaction of newly hired teachers in Congressional District IV, Batangas Province. Specifically, it sought answers to the following questions:

1. What is the degree of job satisfaction of the newly hired teachers as assessed by themselves in terms of:
 - 1.1 teaching-related workload;
 - 1.2. teaching load;
 - 1.3. extra-curricular and non-teaching duties
2. How may the extent of manifestation of workload difficulty be assessed by the respondents relative to:
 - 2.1. teacher retention;
 - 2.2. motivation and engagement;
 - 2.3. Professional commitment?

3. Is there a significant relationship between the assessments of the degree of job satisfaction and the extent of manifestation of workload difficulty?
4. What are the challenges encountered by the newly hired teachers in their workload that may affect job satisfaction?
5. Based on the findings of the study, what engaging activities for newly hired teachers may be proposed?

Methodology

Research Design

The descriptive research design using quantitative techniques was employed as the study focused on the relationship between workload and job satisfaction among newly hired teachers in Congressional District IV in Batangas Province. The research also adopted a quantitative, correlational design, utilizing a self-administered survey questionnaire to collect data from newly hired teachers across various schools within the district. According to Sreekumar (2024) correlational research is a type of non-experimental research that focuses on assessing the relationship between two or more variables. It is presented the degree of satisfaction of teacher in terms of teachers' related workload, and teaching load, and extracurricular activities, and non-teaching duties as well as the extent of manifestation in the degree of workload difficulty.

Participants

Participants of the study were 219 obtained from the 503 total study population through the use of purposive sampling. The purpose intended selection is that the member of the population must be 3 years or less in service. Purposive sampling is a technique where researchers intentionally choose individuals based on the well-defined criteria of the respondents: selected teachers with three years and below teaching experience in Public School in Congressional District IV, Batangas Province (Silverio, B. et al., 2023).

Research Instrument

The researcher used a self-administered survey questionnaire designed to collect comprehensive information on the workload and job satisfaction of the newly hired teachers in Congressional District IV, Batangas Province. The survey was divided into two sections: one focused on measuring teachers' workload and the other focused on assessing their job satisfaction. The research used a four-point likert scale to gauge opinions or attitudes, which often used in surveys or questionnaires, to assess satisfaction or agreement with a statement (Chang, n.d).

Questionnaire. The survey questionnaire consist of four-point Likert scale was administered and distributed to the respondents either in printed form or via Google Form, depending on their convenience and accessibility. Instructions were provided to ensure accurate responses.

Interview Guide. An interview guide is a written framework containing questions, prompts, or themes that direct the flow of a research interview.

Data Collection Procedure

To acquire comprehensive findings of the study, the researcher used various research and conceptual literature to formulate a researcher-made survey questionnaire. The goal of the survey was to collect data regarding the newly hired teachers' degree of satisfaction with the teachers' workload and the respondents' extent of manifestation on the difficulty of the workload itself. The researcher formulates a researcher-made survey questionnaire. The researcher asked permission from the Public Schools District Supervisor to survey a formal letter, which was personally sent to the Division Office. A letter of approval from the PSDS was attached to the survey questionnaire and sent to the School Heads.

Furthermore, a letter asking for permission and assurance of the confidentiality of answers was attached to the respondents' survey questionnaire. To achieve the correct number of respondents' answers, a Google Form was created for the teachers to answer each item more conveniently online. Using the approved and validated interview questions attached to the survey questionnaire of the respondents, the researcher made time to interview the respondents either online (via Google Meet) or in person. The said interview took 20 to 30 minutes. The researcher assured the respondents that their responses would be treated with confidentiality. Information was analyzed and interpreted.

Data Analysis

Descriptive research method (frequency, percentage, ranking, and weighted mean) as well as the Pearson's r were used to summarize responses and identify the relationship of the teachers' workload and job satisfaction.

Results

Table 1

Degree of Job Satisfaction of the Newly Hired Teachers in terms of Teaching-related Workload

Items	WM	SD	VI
1. Observing time-on-task in teaching	3.54	0.499	HS
2. Accomplishing school forms (online and offline forms)	3.07	0.253	MS
3. Monitoring and checking learners' attendance	3.74	0.448	HS
4. Organizing and supervising school activities for the betterment of the learners	3.63	0.494	HS
5. Providing guidance and support to students' academic and other school matters	3.65	0.479	HS
6. Tutoring the students who are part of the ARAL Reading Programs	3.42	0.676	MS
7. Providing intake sheets and incident reports to students when issues arise	3.55	0.499	HS
8. Observing parents' participation and attendance, especially in card giving	3.58	0.495	HS
9. Monitoring learners' Nutritional Status	3.56	0.497	HS
10. Attending and participating in special DepEd projects and activities, such as subject training and workshops.	3.66	0.485	HS
Composite Mean	3.54	0.344	HS

Range of Mean: 3.50-4.00 Highly Satisfied (HS) 1.50-2.49 Slightly Satisfied (SS)

2.50-3.49 Moderately Satisfied (MS) 1.00-1.49 Least Satisfied (LS)

As shown in Table 2, the top three highest mean scores were obtained in monitoring and checking the learners' attendance, attending in DepEd projects and activities, and providing guidance and support to students' academic needs, suggesting that these aspects are viewed most favorably by the respondents.

On the other hand, the lowest mean score was recorded in accomplishing school forms, either online or offline forms, tutoring students who are part of the ARAL Program, and creating intake sheets and incident reports for students when issues arise. These indicate that this area is perceived as less satisfactory compared to others. This finding conformed to the idea of Baxi, b. & Atre, D. et al. (2024) that satisfaction levels vary depending on the nature of tasks and the support provided.

Similarly, Fatahi, Negar, and Warner-Griffin, Catharine. (2024) emphasized that identifying both high and low satisfaction areas is essential for designing interventions that enhance teacher performance and well-being. In general, the respondents are highly satisfied with their teaching-related work. The generated composite mean of 3.54 (SD = 0.344) denotes that teachers are highly satisfied with the teaching-related workload assigned to them. Though teaching-related consists of paperwork, monitoring, tutoring, attending, and participating on

different activities related to the job, they manage to still find satisfaction in their job. workload assigned to them. Though teaching-related consists of paperwork, monitoring, tutoring, attending, and participating on different activities related to the job, they manage to still find satisfaction in their job.

Table 2
Degree of Job Satisfaction of the Newly Hired Teachers in terms of Teaching Load

Items	WM	SD	VI
1. Localizing and indigenizing of MELCs	3.56	0.516	HS
2. Preparing of instructional materials (Lesson Plan and PPT)	3.62	0.497	HS
3. Checking of students' outputs (written works, performance tasks, and summative tests)	3.68	0.466	HS
4. Encoding and recording of students' outputs.	3.63	0.494	HS
5. Providing feedback to each student based on their performance	3.65	0.488	HS
6. Constructing a Table of Specification (TOS) for each quarterly exam	3.57	0.557	HS
7. Constructing Quarterly Exams	3.62	0.506	HS
8. Providing reports as the subject area coordinator	3.54	0.499	HS
9. Providing homeroom guidance and management	3.53	0.518	HS
10. Managing 30-40 students in class	3.34	0.639	MS
Composite Mean	3.57	0.416	HS

Range of Mean: 3.50-4.00 Highly Satisfied (HS) 1.50-2.49 Slightly Satisfied (SS)

2.50-3.49 Moderately Satisfied (MS) 1.00-1.49 Least Satisfied (LS)

Table 2 shows the degree of job satisfaction of the newly hired teachers in terms of teaching load. With a grand mean of 3.57, it clearly indicates that the teachers are highly satisfied with the teaching load. Checking of outputs (written, performance tasks, and quarterly exams), providing feedback to each student's outputs, and encoding and recording students' outputs are the indicators that obtained the highest mean.

According to Tarraya, H. (2023, June 24), heavy workloads influence teachers' overall effectiveness and efficiency. revealed that although heavy workloads lead to some negative outcomes like high emotional stress and feelings of tiredness that hamper the teachers' capability to teach, they still achieve satisfactory ratings even though they are bombarded with designation and responsibility. Teaching load offers practical experience for teachers, which maximizes their professional opportunities and growth and encourages them to be leaders, analytical thinkers, proactive, and initiate progressive practices.

On the other hand, indicators such as managing 30-40 students in class, providing homeroom guidance, and providing reports as subject area coordinator obtained the lowest mean. These findings conform to the idea of Sentones, M. & Villocino, R. (2025), stating that workload is the critical need for effective workload management and targeted burnout prevention strategies to maintain a motivated and satisfied teaching workforce. Additionally, it suggests that large class sizes pose relatively greater challenges compared to other teaching tasks

In general, with the given grand mean of 3.57, which means that newly hired teachers with 0-3 years of teaching experience are highly satisfied with their workload. Thus, critical need for effective workload management and targeted burnout prevention strategies to maintain a motivated and satisfied teaching workforce. This is due to structured support systems, equitable task distribution, and professional development programs that promote a balanced workload.

Table 3
Degree of Job Satisfaction of the Newly Hired Teachers in terms of Extra-curricular and Non-teaching Duties

Items	WM	SD	VI
1. Participation with local organizations for student projects	3.43	0.524	MS
2. Attending LAC (Learning Action Cell)	3.55	0.591	HS
3. participating in environmental activities	3.57	0.540	HS
4. Training and coaching students for athletic competition	3.44	0.591	MS
5. Serving as moderators as an adviser or moderator for student clubs	3.45	0.508	MS
6. Monitoring classroom cleanliness	3.62	0.515	HS
7. Maintaining school facilities	3.53	0.519	HS
8. Shouldering responsibilities for school programs	3.36	0.489	HS
9. Participating in Brigada Eskwela	3.58	0.513	HS
10. Coordinating and supervising various activities and programs within the school	3.45	0.525	MS
Composite Mean	3.50	0.415	HS
<i>Range of Mean: 3.50-4.00 Highly Satisfied (HS)</i>	<i>1.50-2.49 Slightly Satisfied (SS)</i>		
<i>2.50-3.49 Moderately Satisfied (MS)</i>	<i>1.00-1.49 Least Satisfied (LS)</i>		

Table 3 shows the degree of job satisfaction of the newly hired teachers in terms of extra-curricular and non-teaching duties maintaining a conducive learning environment and engaging in collaborative school initiatives. It shows that newly hired teachers are highly satisfied in monitoring the classroom cleanliness (3.64) while participating with local organization for students' projects obtained the lowest mean (3.43).

According to Kouam, A. (2025), educators recognize the necessity of integrating sustainability. Activities such as Birgada Eskwela, environmental activities, and monitoring of classroom cleanliness involve students as well. Thus, the teachers greatly emphasized the importance of sustainability and hands-on activities. These activities promote educational value, skill development, and community involvement.

On the other hand, teachers' participation with local organizations for student projects, training and coaching students for their athletic competition, and serving as moderators as an adviser or advisers for student clubs got the lowest mean. This conforms by Hensch, M. (2020) that teachers often struggle to participate due to time constraints and family obligations. Implications from the study reveal that involvement in extracurricular activities leads to stronger

culturally responsive practices in school. Thus, when culturally responsive practices are needed urgently, administrators should consider strategic ways to prioritize extracurricular involvement.

The grand mean is 3.50, which means that the teachers are highly satisfied with their extra-curricular and non-teaching duties. Thus, it can be inferred that these responsibilities are perceived as manageable and even fulfilling, contributing positively to their overall sense of professional satisfaction. This finding underscores the importance of sustaining supportive structures and recognition for teachers' involvement in activities beyond classroom instruction, as these play a vital role in enhancing both their morale and commitment to the school community

Table 4
Extent of Manifestation of Workload Difficulty of Newly Hired Teachers in terms of Teacher Retention

Items	WM	SD	VI
1. I have students in class who have manageable behaviors	3.27	0.610	MM
2. I have co-teachers who are open to collaboration	3.59	0.546	HM
3. I have a working environment that has a good culture	3.51	0.616	HM
4. I feel appreciated for the efforts I exerted in my teaching career	3.48	0.638	MM
5. I receive training and mentorship from the Principal or School Head	3.50	0.659	MM
6. I experience fairness and transparency in evaluation	3.52	0.608	HM
7. I am content in my work, for I know that it is a stable job	3.65	0.507	HM
8. I know that this profession offers career growth and promotion	3.61	0.559	HM
9. I have family that inspires me	3.72	0.469	HM
10. I receive medical and healthcare benefits	3.21	0.847	MM
Composite Mean	3.51	0.443	HM

Range of Mean: 3.50-4.00 Highly Manifested (HM) 1.50-2.49 Slightly Manifested (SM)

2.50-3.49 Moderately Manifested (MM) 1.00-1.49 Least Manifested (LM)

Table 4 exhibits the extent of manifestation of workload difficulty of the newly hired teachers in terms of teacher retention. The highest-rated items were the items that suggest that teachers have a family that inspires them, their contentment in work, and their knowledge that their work offers growth and stability. These results suggest that family support, job stability, and opportunities for career advancement are the primary factor contributing to teachers' job satisfaction. This indicates that such aspects are strongly manifested within their school context, and therefore, the institution must continue to nurture and strengthen these areas to sustain and further enhance teacher satisfaction.

On the other hand, indicators about medical and healthcare benefits, managing class behaviors, and appreciation exerted in teaching received the lowest mean score. This indicates that teachers perceive limited manifestation in terms of benefits, classroom management, and recognition of their professional contributions. These areas appear to be less positively

experienced compared to other aspects of their workload, suggesting that additional support and interventions are needed to strengthen teacher well-being, improve classroom conditions, and enhance appreciation for their efforts.

This conforms by Brandon, A. (2024), who stated that motivated teachers are likely to be more engaged, perform to their highest potential, and positively affect those around them, while teachers with low motivation may lack interest in their work, disengage from peers and students, and perform at a minimum rate or less.

The grand mean is 3.51 for the extent of manifestation of workload difficulty of newly hired teachers in terms of Teacher Retention, which suggests that despite the challenges associated with workload, newly hired teachers perceive their profession as sustainable and are likely to remain committed. Such findings imply that supportive school environments, growth opportunities, and recognition of teachers' efforts contribute positively to retention.

Table 5
Extent of Manifestation of Workload Difficulty of Newly Hired Teachers
in terms of Motivation and Engagement

Items	WM	SD	VI
1. I have a strong passion for teaching	3.71	0.454	MM
2. I have the desire to influence my students	3.76	0.460	HM
3. I experience a sense of fulfillment and personal development in my work	3.61	0.542	HM
4. I have the right amount of time and energy dedicated to both my job and my personal life	3.34	0.720	MM
5. I find joy and meaning in helping the students grow intellectually and emotionally	3.68	0.498	HM
6. I have a working environment that cultivates respect	3.61	0.567	HM
7. I receive certificates of recognition obtained from student evaluations	3.37	0.732	MM
8. I feel motivated to stay in my job because of the percentage or score gathered from the Performance Management and Evaluation System (PMES) through Classroom Observation	3.46	0.644	MM
9. I receive recognition and appreciation from my colleagues	3.43	0.649	MM
10. I am content with the salary I receive.	3.13	0.785	MM
Composite Mean	3.51	0.432	HM

Range of Mean: 3.50-4.00 Highly Manifested (HM) 1.50-2.49 Slightly Manifested (SM)

2.50-3.49 Moderately Manifested (MM) 1.00-1.49 Least Manifested (LM)

Table 5 presents the extent of manifestation of workload difficulty of the newly hired teachers in terms of motivation and engagement. The highest rated mean is the item that suggests that newly hired teachers have the desire to influence their students, followed by their passion for teaching and the joy they feel in helping the students grow intellectually and emotionally.

This conformed by Cha, W. et.al. (2025), which states that teachers with intrinsic job selection motives held more positive efficacy beliefs and school climate perceptions. Teachers perform well in school if their inner selves are motivated. It is therefore important to give importance to classroom management among teachers with diverse motives, more teacher education and professional development programs addressing classroom discipline and effective behavior management.

On one hand, the items that has lowest mean score are those which are about their salary, time dedicated both to their job and personal life, as well as the recognition they received from the students' evaluation. This suggests that while difficulties are present, they are not overwhelming, and teachers remain committed to their profession. It further implies that supportive school practices, mentoring, and opportunities for professional growth play a significant role in sustaining retention despite workload demands.

General, L. and Masugod, A. (2025) highlighted that in terms of teacher motivation, emphasizing the importance of effective recruitment, training, rewards, and performance management in enhancing teacher motivation is very important. Additionally, a strong positive correlation was identified between pay satisfaction and teacher motivation, indicating that salary levels, benefits, raises, and administrative structures significantly influence teachers' motivation and satisfaction. Furthermore, the study highlighted the importance of teacher recognition. It is found that acknowledging teachers' achievements, whether through small gestures or formal recognition, can greatly enhance their motivation and dedication to their profession.

Table 6
Extent of Manifestation of Workload Difficulty of Newly Hired Teachers
in terms of Professional Commitment

Items	WM	SD	VI
1. I am dedicated to my work/ teaching career.	3.68	0.469	HM
2. I have the intention to retain in the School where I teach now.	3.53	0.644	HM
3. I have a strong passion for continuous learning.	3.70	0.479	HM
4. I adhere to my professional competence	3.70	0.468	HM
5. I am committed in continuos learning	3.78	0.415	HM
6. I know that as a teacher, I can decide what information I can share with my students during class	3.70	0.496	HM
7. I consider taking care of the diversity or differences of my students	3.47	0.652	MM
8. I am happy to fulfill the learners' needs through innovative teaching methods	3.76	0.440	HM
9. I seek to improve the learning areas I teach to improve the level of education	3.74	0.448	HM
10. I have students whose parents are actively involve on their child's academic performance	3.75	0.432	HM
Composite Mean	3.68	0.373	HM

Range of Mean: 3.50-4.00 *Highly Manifested (HM)* 1.50-2.49 *Slightly Manifested (SM)*
 2.50-3.49 *Moderately Manifested (MM)* 1.00-1.49 *Least Manifested (LM)*

Table 6 shows the extent of manifestation of workload difficulty of the newly hired teachers in terms of professional commitment. The highest rated mean for the extent of manifestation of workload Difficulty of Newly Hired Teachers in terms of professional commitment is they are committed in continuous learning, newly hired teachers are also happy to fulfill the needs through innovative teaching methods, they also find satisfaction if the parents are involve the students' academic performance which indicates that newly hired teachers demonstrate strong dedication to professional growth, innovation in teaching, and continuous improvement of instructional practices. These findings suggest that despite workload challenges, teachers remain highly motivated to enhance their competencies and contribute meaningfully to the quality of education, reflecting a deep sense of responsibility and commitment to their profession.

This conformed to Tagaloguin, S. (2025), who stated that teachers uphold strong work ethics and are proactive in pursuing professional development. However, these domains appear not to be directly correlated, implying that external factors may influence growth more than intrinsic values. Furthermore, he added that teachers generally exhibited high levels of work values, particularly in integrity and continuous learning.

Their professional growth was rated very high with strong indicators in career advancement and skill development. On one hand, the indicator that rated the lowest mean is the item that indicates that teachers consider diversity and differences, followed by the teachers' intention to retain in the school, and their dedication to their teaching career. This indicates that while teachers demonstrate commitment to their profession, there are areas where satisfaction and manifestation are relatively weaker. Specifically, challenges in addressing student diversity, sustaining long-term retention, and maintaining consistent dedication suggest that these aspects may require further support and reinforcement. Such findings imply that schools should strengthen inclusive practices, provide retention incentives, and foster programs that continually nurture teachers' professional dedication.

Ryan, M. et.al. (2020), teachers around the world lack confidence in teaching diverse students. This finding supports the present study's results, where lower satisfaction was observed in addressing student diversity. It highlights the need for schools to strengthen professional development programs that equip teachers with the skills and strategies necessary to effectively manage diverse classrooms.

In general, the findings reveal that while teachers demonstrate strong intrinsic motivation and professional commitment, certain external factors such as compensation, recognition, and work-life balance remain areas of concern. The results suggest that teachers derive satisfaction primarily from their passion for teaching, continuous learning, and the meaningful impact they have on students. However, challenges related to benefits, classroom diversity, and retention highlight the need for schools to provide sustained support systems, equitable rewards, and

professional development opportunities. Overall, the study underscores the importance of balancing intrinsic and extrinsic factors to ensure long-term teacher satisfaction and retention.

Table 7
Job Satisfaction (Teaching-related workload) vs. Workload Difficulty

Variables	r-value	df	p-value	Remarks	Decision	Interpretation
Teacher Retention	0.558	217	0.000	Moderate	Reject Ho	Significant
Motivation and Engagement	0.392	217	0.000	Weak	Reject Ho	Significant
Professional Commitment	0.410	217	0.000	Moderate	Reject Ho	Significant

Level of Significance () = 0.05

Table 7 shows a moderate positive correlation between teaching-related work and teacher retention, as evidenced by the generated r-value of 0.558. The obtained p-value of 0.000 is less than the 0.05 level of significance; therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected. This indicates that there is a significant relationship between teaching-related work and the extent of workload difficulty in terms of teacher retention.

This denotes that as teachers engage more in teaching-related tasks, their likelihood of remaining in the profession increases, provided that these tasks are manageable and supported. It further implies that effective workload management and institutional support can strengthen teacher retention by ensuring that teaching responsibilities contribute positively to professional commitment rather than becoming sources of job dissatisfaction.

This conformed to the study of Maquidato, J. & Bayani, R. (2024), indicating that a high level of workload among teachers significantly impacts teacher productivity and general performance. The results indicate that teachers face substantial duties and obligations, perceiving their workload as demanding in terms of time and energy. Teachers report difficulties in managing their energy, often stretching themselves beyond capacity and experiencing fatigue that affects the quality of their work. The study emphasizes the complex nature of teacher workload, which involves not only instructional duties but also significant demands on energy and time management.

Meanwhile, Table 9 showcases the significant relationship between teaching load and the extent of manifestation of workload difficulty in terms of teacher retention, motivation, engagement, and professional commitment

Table 8
Job Satisfaction (Teaching Load) vs. Manifestation of Workload Difficulty

Variables	r-value	df	P-value	Remarks	Decision	Interpretation
Teacher Retention	-0.002	217	0.978	Very Weak	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
Motivation and Engagement	0.041	21	0.548	Very Weak	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
Professional Commitment	0.013	217	0.848	Very Weak	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant

Level of Significance () = 0.05

As can be seen on the table 8, there is a very weak negative correlation between teaching load and teacher retention, as evidenced by the generated r-value of -0.002. The obtained p-value of 0.978 is greater than the 0.05 level of significance; therefore, the null hypothesis is not rejected. This indicates that there is no significant relationship between teaching load and the extent of workload difficulty in terms of teacher retention. This denotes that the number of the workload or subjects assigned to teachers does not directly influence their decision to remain in the profession. Instead, other factors such as intrinsic motivation, professional commitment, and institutional support may play a more decisive role in sustaining teacher retention.

This conformed to the study of Magalong, A. & Torreon, L. (2021), which states that teaching effectiveness does not depend on the tasks and functions given to the teachers; hence, they are still able to achieve a satisfactory rating despite the fact that they are bombarded with designation and responsibility. Similarly, the present findings suggest that teachers remain committed to their professional duties and continue to demonstrate effectiveness even when faced with workload challenges. This highlights the resilience and intrinsic motivation of educators, underscoring that their dedication to student learning often outweighs the pressures of additional responsibilities

Table 9
Job Satisfaction (Extra-curricular and non-teaching duties) vs. Manifestation of Workload Difficulty

Variables	r-value	df	P-value	Remarks	Decision	Interpretation
Teacher Retention	0.581	217	0.000	Moderate	Reject Ho	Significant
Motivation and Engagement	0.462	217	0.000	Moderate	Reject Ho	Significant
Professional Commitment	0.363	217	0.000	Moderate	Reject Ho	Significant

Level of Significance () = 0.05

Table 9 shows a moderate positive correlation between extra-curricular and non-teaching duties and teacher retention, as evidenced by the generated r-value of 0.581. The obtained p-value of 0.000 is less than the 0.05 level of significance; therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected. This indicates that there is a significant relationship between teaching-related work and the extent of workload difficulty in terms of teacher retention.

This denotes that teachers' participation in extra-curricular and non-teaching responsibilities positively influences their commitment to remain in the profession. When these duties are supported and recognized, they foster a stronger sense of belonging, professional fulfillment, and engagement within the school community. Conversely, if such tasks are poorly managed or overly burdensome, they may contribute to stress and hinder retention. Thus, balanced workload distribution and institutional support are essential to ensure that these responsibilities enhance rather than diminish teacher satisfaction and retention.

This conformed to the study of Aulilia, N., and Haerani (2022), stating that compensation, familial issues, teamwork, and social culture have a significant role in keeping teachers in their positions. It was also highlighted in their study that fostering camaraderie and teamwork may reduce teacher attrition and turnover.

Table 10
Challenges Encountered by Newly Hired Teachers in their Workload that may Affect Job Satisfaction

Items	WM	SD	VI
1. Lack of familiarity in creating a lesson plan with the latest teaching strategies and techniques	1.93	0.650	S
2. Inadequate teaching tools and learning materials	1.95	0.708	S
3. Difficulty in handling multi-grade classes	1.78	0.734	S
4. Subject mismatch	1.63	0.726	S
5. Lack of knowledge in technology integration	1.53	0.652	S
6. Lack of effective communication with colleagues and administrators	1.74	0.731	S
7. Lacks proper classroom management skills	1.54	0.644	S
8. Lack of time management	1.76	0.722	S
9. Poor communication with parents	1.51	0.631	S
10. Poor work-life balance	1.70	0.671	S
Composite Mean	1.71	0.452	S

Range of Mean: 3.50-4.00 Always (A) 1.50-2.49 Sometimes (S)

 2.50-3.49 Often (O) 1.00-1.49 Never (N)

Table 10 shows that a lack of familiarity in creating lesson plans with the latest teaching strategies and techniques sometimes affects job satisfaction. The obtained weighted mean of 1.93 (SD = 0.650) suggests that most teachers are confident and capable in preparing lesson plans aligned with updated strategies and techniques, and such challenges are not a significant source of dissatisfaction. This indicates that teachers generally possess adequate knowledge and skills in lesson planning, enabling them to integrate modern strategies effectively into their teaching practice. It further implies that professional development initiatives and training programs have been successful in equipping teachers with the necessary competencies, thereby minimizing the negative impact of lesson planning difficulties on their overall job satisfaction.

It is also noted in the table that inadequacy in teaching tools and difficulty in handling multi-grade classes sometimes affect teachers' job satisfaction. Thus, the presence of these issues highlights the importance of ensuring adequate instructional resources and providing specialized support for teachers assigned to multi-grade classrooms. Resolving these concerns can further strengthen teacher satisfaction and enhance the overall quality of instruction delivered in diverse educational settings.

It conformed to the idea of Onde, R. (2023), which states that lesson planning has no significant relationship to the teachers' job satisfaction. Also, being resilient and versatile in managing the challenges met in teaching multigrade classes, effective coping mechanisms can be practiced by teachers to improve learners' performance. Further, teachers' resilience in facing multi-grade classes is important.

Similarly to the result of the survey, the findings affirm that teachers' job satisfaction is not primarily hindered by lesson planning difficulties or the challenges of handling multi-grade classes. Instead, their resilience, adaptability, and professional commitment enable them to maintain effectiveness despite these responsibilities. This suggests that while certain workload factors may occasionally pose difficulties, they do not significantly diminish overall satisfaction when teachers are equipped with adequate coping mechanisms, institutional support, and access to necessary resources.

The respondents are likewise highly satisfied to perform their professional responsibilities and accomplish their roles as educators. This suggests that they derive a strong sense of accomplishment and motivation from their teaching duties, which contributes positively to their overall job satisfaction. Their high level of satisfaction reflects not only their commitment to instructional tasks but also their resilience in managing challenges within the educational environment. Such findings emphasize that teachers' dedication and passion for their work remain central factors in sustaining both effectiveness and retention in the profession.

Inadequate teaching tools and the challenges of handling multi-grade classes, which, although not frequently encountered, still pose difficulties for some educators. Such issues highlight the importance of providing sufficient instructional resources and targeted support systems, particularly for teachers managing diverse classroom settings. Addressing these concerns can further enhance teacher satisfaction and ensure that workload challenges do not compromise instructional quality.

In general, the respondents reveal that challenges they encountered relative to their workload sometimes affect their job satisfaction. The generated composite mean of 1.72 (SD = 0.452) denotes that while workload-related issues may sometimes arise, they are not frequent enough to significantly decline overall job satisfaction. It further infers that teachers are largely able to manage their responsibilities effectively, and that institutional support and professional resilience help minimize the negative impact of workload difficulties.

This conformed to the study of Kapur, R. (2022) which states that inadequate teaching-learning methods and materials are unfavorable to the overall educational system. According to his study, to further improve teaching-learning materials, it is essential to understand the academic concepts appropriately, teachers should become well-prepared, and be well-versed in terms of academic needs. Schools should also identify the academic needs, as a result, this will enrich the overall education system.

Discussion

The findings suggest that newly hired teachers are highly satisfied to their teaching load, teaching-related workload, and extra-curricular duties and non-teaching tasks have significant relationship to newly hired teachers' job satisfaction. Also, it is evident in the study that the newly hired teachers' manifestation to their workload difficulty in terms of teacher retention, motivation and engagement, and professional commitment is highly manifested. This is

consistent to the existing literature that teachers' workload has significant relationship to the teachers job satisfaction. (Tarraya, H. 2023, June 24; Jomuad, P. et al., 2021).

In addition, the study revealed that the lack of adequate teaching and learning materials is the most significant challenge affecting teachers' job satisfaction next is the lack of familiarity in creating a lesson plan with the latest teaching strategies and techniques. It is therefore important to adhere these challenges to attain high level of job satisfaction among newly hired teachers.

Based on these findings, the research emphasizes the importance for institutions and DepEd to develop strategic plans that not only alleviate teachers' workload but also ensure tasks are distributed more equitably.

Conclusion

The study demonstrated that newly hired teachers showed high satisfaction with their teaching responsibilities. Also, their extent of manifestation of workload difficulty in teaching was assessed as high. In addition, the assessments on the degree of job satisfaction in terms of teaching-related workload and extra-curricular and non-teaching duties were found to be significantly related to all the variables on workload difficulty. It is also noted in the study that the top two common challenges of teachers are their lack of familiarity in creating lesson plan using the latest strategies and techniques as well as the inadequate teaching tools and learning materials. Furthermore, findings of the study about the teachers' workload and job satisfaction clearly indicate that the workload of teachers has a significant relationship to their job satisfaction.

Furthermore, since the study is limited to newly hired teachers in Congressional District IV, Batangas Province, further studies across the region are suggested to gain a broader understanding of the workload challenges faced by new educators. Such insights would enable DepEd to strengthen recruitment strategies among newly hired teachers, and implement measures that help reduce early resignation rates as well as solved the issues regarding the teaching and learning materials.

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